

**SHADOW REPORT ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE
FRAMEWORK CONVENTION FOR PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF
NATIONAL MINORITIES IN ROMANIA**

Concerning

**The discrimination and unequal access to secondary and tertiary
education of Hungarian and Hungarian-speaking Roma students**

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The report was submitted by Bálványos Institute and Romanian Society for Intercultural and Migration Studies (SoSIM).

Bálványos Institute is a think tank based in Cluj-Napoca/Kolozsvár conducting social and public policy research on topics concerning the Hungarian community in Transylvania. The Institute, publishes research reports, sociological studies and public policy analyses, based on empirical research and analysis, directed at decision makers, NGOs and civil advocacy groups.

The Romanian Society for Intercultural and Migration Studies (SoSIM) was established in 2024 to meet the new challenges emerging from Romania's transformation into a transnational contact zone, where diverging perspectives of development, changing labour relations, and intensifying human mobility actively interact, intersect, and grapple with each other. As Romania becomes a destination country for third-country nationals, particularly from Asia, finding a more complex and human approach to human mobility has become an urgent matter to us. In line with this, we look for a third way of addressing and transcending the confrontation between utilitarian and culturalist views around development, labour, and migration; the persistence of internal inequalities in class, socio-geographic, ethnic, racial, and gender terms; and the hierarchical structuring of immigration under the prerequisites of global racial capitalism. At SoSIM we commit to filling the intellectual gaps and mitigating the injustices and violences that emerge in this process.

The report was written by Tamás Kiss (SoSIM), sociologist and civic activist and Tibor Toró (Bálványos Institute), political scientist and civic activist.

Executive summary

Our shadow focuses on Hungarian language education and investigates the implementation of FCNM (primarily of Articles 4, 12 and 6), for the 6th reporting period based on an exhaustive survey of Hungarian and mixed language schools conducted in 2024 and secondary analysis of statistical data. Although it is not our primary focus, we also reflect upon legislative changes concerning education of minority children during the 6th implementation period.

Law no. 198/2023 on Education recognizes the right of minorities to education in/of their mother tongue at all levels and all forms of education. The law also calls for (or makes possible) a strong form of minority language education. In minority schools all subjects might be taught in native language, except – obviously – Romanian language and literature. The legislation leaves large space for multicultural curriculum content, allowing for five subjects (native language and literature, Romanian language and literature, musical education, religious education and history and traditions of minorities) to be thought according to special minority curricula. Moreover, the law encourages the formation of separate minority language schools and guarantees some limited forms of minority control over the educational process. As a result, a state financed and quasi-separate system of Hungarian language education was created, with an increasing proportion of Hungarian students educated in their mother tongue, increasing weight of Hungarian only-schools instead of mixed Romanian-Hungarian ones, increasing Hungarian language use and increasing emphasis on minority-specific curriculum content.

While such an institutional outcome might seem to fulfill requirements under the FCNM – especially those enlisted by Article 14 – and experts often characterize the minority education system in Romania as an example of successful pluralistic approach to diversity management, our empirical research demonstrated that the situation on the ground is far from ideal. We argue that a proper evaluation of Romanian educational policies requires a more systematic empirical investigation (taking into account both legislative elements, their implementation and the outcomes of educational policies) in order to assess whether Romania in fact implemented the education related articles of the FCNM.

Our report focuses less on the right for native language education and more on structural discrimination and unequal access to different levels of education of Hungarian learning students in general and Hungarian-speaking Roma students in particular. Students of Roma origin constitute more than 20% of educational cohorts starting preliminary grade in Hungarian language but disappear almost entirely at upper secondary level. We discuss in details the following aspects:

- 1) Educational rights of Hungarian speaking children in general, namely:
 - a. Disparities in school infrastructure (Article 4)
 - b. Unequal access to auxiliary services such as school psychologist and speech therapist, as a form of structural discrimination (Article 4)
 - c. Unequal access to state financed and school organized extra-curricular activities of Hungarian-learning students, also as a form of structural discrimination (Article 4)
 - d. Linguistic asymmetries and unequal contact in mixed schools (linguistic landscape, extracurricular language use) that can be perceived as discriminatory to Hungarian students (Article 4) and certainly is contrary the minority-majority relations based on equality and mutual respect (Articles 6 and 12.2)

- e. Unequal access to different educational levels due to higher drop-out rate and lower passing rates of official examination (Articles 12.3 and 4.2)
- 2) Educational rights of Hungarian speaking Roma children
- a. Educational segregation of Roma children in Hungarian language education that according to the Romanian legislation should be considered a rather severe form of discrimination and, thus, hinders the implementation of Article 4 of FCNM
 - b. Differences in school infrastructure between segregated Roma schools and other educational units teaching in Hungarian as a form of discrimination strongly connected to educational segregation (Article 4)
 - c. Dramatically high drop-out rates of Hungarian speaking Roma children resulting in unequal access of Roma students to both secondary and tertiary education (Articles 12.3 and 4.2)

Our conclusion is that due to shortcomings in these dimensions it is doubtful whether Romania implemented properly articles 4, 6 and 12 of the Framework Convention. In more substantive terms, we do not argue that Romania would have any obligation connected to FCNM to channel financial resources into such strong and robust form of Hungarian language education as it does. However, though establishing a quasi-separate system of minority education it did not absolve its obligations to provide equal resources and equal access for minority students and to monitor whether Roma students are discriminated against inside the Hungarian language schools.

(1) Discrimination of students learning in Hungarian (Article 4)

The issue of discrimination is rarely discussed in case of linguistically separated educational systems based on voluntary enrollment. Nevertheless, the requirement to provide equal resources and education of equal quality for minority students is a legitimate requirement in case of institutionally robust state financed systems of minority language education too. Neither FCNM, nor other international treaties obliged Romania to create a state-financed quasi-parallel institutional system of minority education. However, if – due to internal processes of bargaining – Romanian legislators decided to do so and if institutional realities have evolved accordingly, there is an obligation to provide equal resources for minority language schools and classes in order to ensure education of equal quality for minority children. The opposite leads to the marginalization of the minority group and cannot be regarded otherwise than structural discrimination.

According to our survey Hungarian language schools, especially in rural areas and in the Hungarian majority countries of Harghita and Covasna are still less equipped with gyms, ballrooms, medical and psychologist's offices, while differences in resource allocation (modern teaching equipment in classrooms) inside mixed schools has diminished considerably between 2019 and 2024. Nevertheless, no systematic official monitoring system of internal resource allocation was created. In order to solve this problem, our first recommendation is:

Monitor and bridge the infrastructural gap

Recommendation 1 (for Article 4)

Relevant authorities should regularly monitor inequalities existing inside mixed schools between Romanian-language medium and Hungarian-language medium classes and should intervene in cases where minority students are discriminated in recourse allocation. One possible solution would be to empower and allocate budgetary support for the Romanian Institute for Research of National Minorities to run the exhaustive survey focusing on minority and mixed language schools at bi- or triannual bases in cooperation with the Ministry of Education and the National Council for Combatting Discrimination as part of the official monitoring process.

Recommendation 2 (for Article 4)

Relevant authorities also should develop evidence-based policies and establish a dedicated state-funding mechanism to rehabilitate fully Hungarian-language educational facilities, prioritizing the construction of gyms, laboratories, libraries, and counseling offices to bring these schools up to the physical standards of mixed-language schools.

According to the decision 172/04.05.2011 of the National Council for Combating Discrimination (NCCD), the lack of bilingual signs inside and at the façade of schools should be considered discrimination and a violation of the rights of minorities to use their language in extracurricular context. Maybe also taking in consideration this statement, the 198/2023 Law on Education regulated explicitly extra-curricular language use. The law made mandatory the bilingual inscriptions inside and at the façade of the schools, as-well-as the employment of minority language-speaking personnel in case of psychologists and speech therapists. It also prescribes the use of minority languages in the internal and external communication of schools (toward students and parents).

In spite of these positive developments, however, our exhaustive survey demonstrated that extra-curricular language use and linguistic landscape within mixed schools remained profoundly asymmetric and this establishes a hierarchical relation between minority and majority students attending these schools. Although these schools have parallel Romanian and Hungarian language streams, the linguistic landscape of these institutions is, in many cases, dominantly Romanian, Hungarian language being limited to in-classroom use. Furthermore, as a result of lack of Hungarian speaking staff, a large number of Hungarian speaking school-children is denied the possibility to use their mother tongue when contacting the speech therapist, or the school psychologist.

Recommendation 3 (for Article 4) – Enforce bilingual landscape

More balanced bilingualism, symmetric extracurricular language use, and balanced linguistic landscape should be facilitated in mixed schools in order avoid the discrimination of Hungarian speaking students. Relevant authorities should regularly monitor this process, as it is explicitly regulated by the educational legislation. One possible solution would be to task and allocate budgetary support for the Romanian Institute for Research National Minorities to conduct in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and the National Council for Combating Discrimination

(NCCD) systematic audits of schools teaching in the minority language to ensure compliance with Article 59, Paragraph 11 of Law no. 198/2023. Clear deadlines and administrative sanctions must be implemented for schools failing to provide bilingual internal signs, timetables, websites, and official announcements.

Recommendation 4 (for Article 4) – Linguistic competence of auxiliary personnel

Hiring of Hungarian speaking personnel in the key positions of school psychologist, speech therapist in mixed medium language schools should be facilitated in order to provide equal access to these services for Hungarian-speaking students. This process should be also officially monitored.

Also, broaden the linguistic requirements of Law no. 198/2023 to mandate that auxiliary, administrative, and medical staff (secretaries, librarians, nurses, and security guards) in mixed schools possess minority-language skills in the minority language that the school teaches in.

Public finances for extracurricular activities are also rather unevenly distributed. Hungarian language programs exist only in the two Hungarian majority counties of Harghita/Hargita and Covasna/Kovászna. Theoretically, this could mean that state financed extracurricular activities represent an integrated segment of education where teachers and student of different background meet each-other. However, practically, this is not the case and students learning in Hungarian language medium schools (outside the above mentioned two countries) have a limited access to extra-curricular activities. This is the most evident in case of language-related activities such as acting, literary circles etc. Our exhaustive survey also demonstrated that in mixed language schools access to extracurricular activities of students learning in Hungarian is rather limited.

Recommendation 5 (for Article 4) – Promote inclusive and minority language extracurricular activities

Hungarian language extra-curricular activities should be financed in all counties, preferably in a proportion equal to the share of students learning Hungarian language medium classes. This is the most justified in areas where Hungarians live in higher proportions and concentrated (Mureş/Maros, Satu-Mare/Szatmár, Bihar/Bihor, Sălaj/Szilágy) and in case of language related activities.

Minority-language extracurricular activities (theaters, music, school media, and student councils) should also have been promoted in mixed language schools to prevent the cultural exclusion and alienation of Hungarian pupils.

(2) Asymmetrical contact between Hungarian and Romanian speaking students in mixed schools (Articles 6 and 12.2)

Discrimination of Hungarian students and asymmetries in extracurricular language use in mixed schools are problematic from another perspective too. These aspects affect the process of socialization of schoolchildren and reproduce the perception that minority members should accept a subordinate

position. If in mixed schools Hungarian students are marginalized and discriminated against, these institutions will barely produce mutual respect and a spirit of tolerance.

Indeed, discriminative practices and asymmetric institutional environment are often evoked by experts and stakeholders when justifying pursuits for separate Hungarian-medium-language schools. These considerations also inform the choices of Hungarian parents when they enroll their children in separate instead of mixed language medium schools. If there were more equal relations between minority and majority students inside these schools, more Hungarian parents would prefer to enroll their children in mixed schools

Recommendation 6 (for Article 6 and 12.2) – Promote symmetric contact in mixed language schools

More equal relation should be promoted inside mixed schools. This should cover both in-school resource allocation and extra-curricular language use. Treating this problem would be necessary to increase the prestige and sustainability of mixed language medium schools.

(3) Educational segregation of Hungarian-speaking Roma children

More than 55% of Roma students enrolled in Hungarian language education study in segregated, Roma-majority educational units, characterized by severe infrastructural deficits, lack of auxiliary services and a low proportion of qualified educators. Educational segregation is also the main driver of the devastating dropout rate in lower secondary education. In Roma majority schools only 6% of the 8th grade students take the national examination, while earlier dropout rates are also far higher than the average among them. Educational segregation of Hungarian-speaking Roma children does not only run against the fundamental principles of the Romanian legislation but, as a severe form of discrimination, is also against the implementation of Article 4 of FCNM.

Combating segregation of Roma children in Hungarian language education (for Article 4)

Recommendation 7 – Monitor and develop evidence-based policies

Official process of monitoring of school segregation of Roma children should be started, including inter-school segregation. Evidence based policies to prevent school segregation should be developed. A concrete, time-bound national strategy to phase out segregated, Roma-majority educational units should be elaborated and implemented, with specific funding lines allocated to the integration of Hungarian-speaking Roma children in the Hungarian medium education.

Recommendation 8 – Eradicate infrastructural inequalities, ban “container schools”

Resource and infrastructural asymmetries should be eradicated by establishing a funding mechanism to upgrade physical infrastructure, digital tools, and classroom environments in marginalized and

segregated rural and urban schools. Crucially, the Ministry of Education must ban the use of "container schools" as a permanent or long-term alternative to physical integration, ensuring all students have equal access to standard school facilities.

Recommendation 9 – Qualified personnel in Roma majority schools

Introduce financial and professional incentives (e.g., allowances, career acceleration points) to attract and retain certified, highly qualified educators in segregated, and rural schools.

Recommendation 10 – Monitor school zoning and ban discriminatory “gerrymandering”

Ban discriminatory school-zoning and administrative gerrymandering. The Ministry of Education, in conjunction with the National Council for Combating Discrimination (CNCD), must audit local school-zoning boundaries and municipal bus routes to ensure they are not being actively used to bypass neighborhood integration and channel Roma children to peripheral schools.

Recommendation 11 - Eradicate identity document barriers to education.

The Ministry of Internal Affairs and local municipalities must end the practice of issuing temporary identity cards to Roma families as a tool of spatial containment. All children, regardless of their parents' housing registration status, must be granted full, unconditional enrollment rights in the public schools closest to their real physical place of residence.

Recommendation 12 - Enforce strict accountability for local school inspectorates.

Establish a monitoring mechanism to investigate and penalize county-level school inspectorates that artificially adjust student enrollment caps for any reason whatsoever, and school directories who systematically reject Roma applicants to keep “non-Roma” schools homogenous.

(4) Facilitating more equal access of Hungarian students to secondary and tertiary education (recommendations in relation to Article 12.3. and 4.2.)

The most serious problem affecting Hungarian-language education as a whole is that students studying in Hungarian reach the 12th grade and pass baccalaureate examination well below the national average. In this regard, we identified three factors conducting to dropout and earlier school-leaving. (1) The dropout between grades 5 and 8, affects disproportionately Roma students, who make up about 20 percent of the student population educated in Hungarian at primary level. (2) unfavorable structure of Hungarian language secondary education and channeling Hungarian students toward short-term secondary education; (3) Lower passing rates of Hungarian students at 8th grade National Evaluation and Baccalaureate examination.

Recommendation 13. – Use separate subsample for students learning in Hungarian for quality assurance (for Article 4.2 and 12.1)

In Romania a representative subsample of PISA for student learning in Hungarian is a highly relevant tool of quality assurance, especially given the low passing rate at baccalaureate examination. Keep the practice of elaborating representative Hungarian-language sample introduced for the first time in 2022.

Recommendation 14. – Calibrate Romanian language and literature examination 8th grade National Evaluation and Baccalaureate Examination

Calibrate the lower secondary Romanian language and literature curriculum for minority speakers and 8th grade Romanian exam for non-native speakers. Urgent reform is needed for the lower secondary Romanian language and literature curriculum and the 8th grade National Evaluation in Romanian Language and Literature. The exam and the specialized curriculum must be fully calibrated to minority children studying in minority languages, ensuring that it test reflects the linguistic competences of minority children.

Recommendation 15 – More balanced structure of upper secondary education

A more balanced structure of Hungarian language upper secondary education is needed with less emphasis on short term and more emphasis on long term forms. Stop channeling disproportionately Hungarian-speaking students into short term upper secondary education.

1. Introduction and general overview

Hungarian language education in Romania constitutes the focus of our shadow report, in which we provide an analysis of the implementation of relevant FCNM provisions. We focus on primary and secondary education and less on pre-primary and tertiary levels. Right to education is a fundamental human right in itself as well as a precondition for enjoyment of other rights, including meaningful societal participation. With regards to education of minority children, the *Commentary on Education under the FCNM* differentiates between two categories of aims. On the one hand, education develops skills and capabilities that help minority children to participate on equal footing in socio-economic life and public affairs. Well educated minority group members may find adequate employment, may have more chances to influence decision making, and, generally speaking, may experience social mobility. These are called instrumental aims. On the other hand, education is expected to respect the child's identity and cultural heritage.¹ Consequently, educational policies targeting minorities should balance between these two principles, namely preserving identity and providing equal opportunities for social mobility. While educational policies in Romania are highly effective in identity preservation, they systematically reproduce inequalities, marginalize members of the Hungarian speaking minority and even more Hungarian speaking Roma. Consequently, they lead to discrimination of Hungarian speaking children, especially of those of Roma origin.

In the following sections, we present results of our empirical research conducted in 2024 focusing. The investigation focused on:

- 3) Educational rights of Hungarian speaking children in general, namely:
 - a. Differences in school infrastructure and teaching equipment between schools
 - b. Lack of Hungarian speaking auxiliary personnel
 - c. Linguistic asymmetries in mixed schools (linguistic landscape, extracurricular language use)
 - d. Unequal access to different educational levels due to higher drop-out rate and lower passing rates of official examination of Hungarian speaking students
- 4) Educational rights of Hungarian speaking Roma children
 - a. Educational segregation of Roma children in Hungarian language education
 - b. Differences in school infrastructure between segregated Roma schools and other educational units teaching in Hungarian
 - c. Dramatically high drop-out rates of Hungarian speaking Roma children

In the first part of the educational section, we briefly outline the major processes affecting Hungarian language education in Romania. We also outline legislative changes, as a new Educational Law was adopted in 2023 (Law no. 198/2023). Further, we introduce the topic of Hungarian-speaking Roma, present some overall trends affecting this population focusing on intersectional discrimination they face with. We also unpack and specify our claims in relation to implementation of educational rights of minorities in Romania and present data sources and research methods we used. In the second part

¹ Advisory Committee on the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities (ACFC): *Commentary on Education under the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities*. ACFC/25DOC(2006)002, Strasbourg, 2 March 2006: 8.

of the report, we present the results of our empirical investigation in the form of article-by-article assessment. The third part includes our concluding remarks and recommendations.

1.1. Romania's educational legislation and general processes affecting Hungarian language education

Hungarian language education in Romania is considered a rather robust form of minority language education. Law no. 198/2023 on education was adopted during the 6th implementation period preserving and extending the educational rights of minorities. The following aspects should be underscored:

- According to the law, **minorities have the right to be educated in their mother tongue**. This means that Romania has committed itself to establish state financed minority language educational institutions (“groups”, “classes”, “sections” or “schools”) upon the request of the parents.²
- The law calls for (or makes possible³) a **medium-of-instruction policy based on the dominance of minority languages**. In pre-university education, all the subjects might be thought in minority languages, with the exception of the Romanian language and literature.⁴ History and geography are to be taught in native language but according to the curriculum of the Romanian counterpart, toponyms and names should be indicated in Romanian as well.⁵ Similarly, special terminology in the case of professional upper secondary and post-secondary education should be taught in Romanian alongside the native language.⁶
- A strong emphasis is put on **multicultural curriculum** in minority education. Para. 4 of Art. 60 enlists three subjects, namely minority language and literature, musical education and history and tradition of minorities which are thought according to special curricula in minority classes/schools. One might add that education of Romanian language and literature is also based on specific curricula developed for minorities,⁷ while religious education – in case of cults practiced overwhelmingly by Hungarians⁸ – also relies on textbooks produced in Hungarian language. All in all, five subjects are taught according to specific curricula developed for minorities.
- The law encourages the creation of **separate minority language schools**. According to Par. 8 of Art. 16, in municipalities where there are several educational units teaching in minority language one educational unit with legal personality (e.g., a separate minority language school) should be created.

² Law no. 198/2023 on Education: Para. 1 and 3 of Art. 59.

³ In case of some smaller minority groups, such as Ukrainians, Croats, Turks etc. Romanian language predominates, even if (officially) minority language education operates.

⁴ Law no. 198/2023 on Education: Para. 1. of Art 60.

⁵ Art. 60, par. 13.

⁶ Art. 60, par. 6.

⁷ Art 60, par. 3.

⁸ The vast majority of Hungarians belong to Reformed, Unitarian and Roman Catholic churches.

- The law even guarantees some (limited) **forms of minority control** over the educational process and educational institutions. Minorities have the right to proportional representation in school management⁹ and county level school inspectorates.¹⁰ This means that even in case of mixed (Romanian and minority language) schools at least the vice-chair should belong to the minority group.¹¹

Due to the above-mentioned elements, experts often characterize the minority education system in Romania as an example of successful pluralistic approach to diversity management. Nonetheless, as we will demonstrate in the following section of the report, the situation on the ground is far from ideal. As a result of this pluralistic approach, there is an ongoing separation of the institutional environment where Hungarian students are educated. Data provided by the Ministry of Education show that an increasing proportion of Hungarian students are enrolled in minority language education. Moreover, there is an increase in the proportion of those attending separate Hungarian schools among students enrolled in Hungarian language-medium education. Figure 1. compares 2012, 2019 and 2023 data, covering the period following adoption of the previous (1/2001) Law on Education. This law introduced for the first time the paragraph mentioned above stipulating the creation of separate Hungarian language educational units. The reasons of the increase are, nevertheless, multiple of the increase of those enrolled in separate Hungarian schools (58% in 2011 and 67% in 2023) in multiple. Due to demographic processes Hungarians are increasingly concentrated in ethnic block areas where Hungarian-only schools prevail. The direct effect of the educational legislation is also visible, especially in ethnically mixed small towns,¹² where separate Hungarian schools were created, while at the same time Hungarian classes in mixed schools were abolished.

⁹ Art 60, par. 8.

¹⁰ Art 116, par. 7

¹¹ Law no. 198/2023 on Education: Para. 7. of Art 59.

¹² The most important cases are Salonta/Nagyszalonta, Marghita/Margitta and Gherla/Szamosújvár.

Figure 1. Students learning in Hungarian medium language schools

Source: Calculations based on aggregated SIIR databases

The overall outcome of these processes was the creation of a quasi-separate state financed system¹³ of Hungarian-language education. This is a possible solution for minority language education and in line with ACFC recommendations. The *Commentary on Education* explains a general preference for dual language (or, as it is called in the document, bilingual) education but also acknowledges that in some cases “*separate teaching, in whole or in part may be more appropriate, or even the only possible solution*”.¹⁴

From this perspective, Romania has formally guaranteed most Hungarian educational rights. These include education in Hungarian language, Romanian language taught based on a special curriculum (teaching as a second language), separate minority administered schools, inclusion of elements of the Hungarian national canon in the minority curriculum. Indeed, Law no. 198/2023 on education provides important possibilities for minority decision-making.

¹³ At primary and secondary level private schools are insignificant. See Annex 1 – Table 6.

¹⁴ ACFC: *Commentary on Education*, 17.

1.2. Hungarian speaking Roma facing intersectional and multiple inequalities

According to SocioRoMap survey carried out by Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities (ISPMN),¹⁵ Hungarian-speakers are heavily overrepresented among those living in compact Roma neighborhoods (colonies, blocks, quarters, settlements etc.). They represent 11 percent of the approximately 750,000 people living in such neighborhoods. The total number of Hungarian-speaking Roma in Romania (including those living dispersed among non-Roma) is around 105,000. There are two large Hungarian-speaking Roma blocks, one in Harghita, Covasna and Mureş counties (approx. 50,000 people) and one in Bihor and Satu-Mare counties (approx. 35,000 people). There are 300 compact Roma neighborhoods where practically exclusively Hungarian is spoken and an additional 150 neighborhoods with a strong presence of the Hungarian language.

Three aspects characterize the situation of Hungarian-speaking Roma. First, they are strongly connected to the minority institutions of the Hungarian community. Not only they do speak Hungarian but their children are enrolled in Hungarian schools, they belong to Hungarian churches, and vote for Hungarian ethnic parties. Second, they are (virtually) invisible at the level of official and public representations. They barely appear in census figures, are not included in historical narratives and there are no Roma-related public memorials in Hungarian-speaking areas. Third, their connection to the Hungarians does not translate into equal participation in Hungarian minority institutions.

Moreover, SocioRoMap data on housing conditions show that their situation is more dire than that of Roma in general. In their neighborhoods the quality of private and community infrastructure is worse, more houses are overcrowded, low quality and deteriorated buildings are more common. They are also less integrated into the labor market (through formal long-term employment) and a greater proportion of them lives in poverty.

There are multiple causes contributing to this unfavorable situation. According to survey results, social differences between Roma and non-Roma are larger in the case of Hungarian speakers, while territories inhabited by Hungarian-speaking Roma (and Hungarians in general) are economically peripheral. Moreover, Roma strategies fail to address their specific situation, increased vulnerability and multiple and intersectional discrimination experienced by this community. They are barely included in existing projects of Roma inclusion.

1.2.1. Romania's legislation on educational segregation

Romania's educational legislation is rather unequivocal regarding educational segregation. Law no. 198/2003 strictly prohibits educational segregation at all levels¹⁶ and clearly states that segregation should be considered a severe form of discrimination being, thus, against the fundamental principles

¹⁵ See: <https://eeagrants.org/en/fmo/areas-work/programmes-and-projects-information/archive/2009-2014/projects/ro25-0004>; <https://statisztikak.erdelystat.ro/cikkek/magyarul-besz-el-romak-erdelyben-terleti-elhelyezkedes-es-lakohelyi-szegregacio/60>.

¹⁶ Art 79.

of Romania's educational legislation and policies.¹⁷ Under Article 11 the following exemptions are enlisted and not considered as educational segregation:

- 1) Special educational units designed for students with severe disabilities;
- 2) Native language education provided by the Romanian state for national minorities;
- 3) Groups accommodating immigrants or refugees.

Theoretically, Romani language education is integrated into Romania's educational system and "mother tongue track", where some or most subjects are taught in Romani is a possible option of Roma children. In practice, however, the vast majority of Roma children are enrolled in either Romanian or Hungarian language education. Some (but not the majority) of these students enrolled in Romanian or Hungarian language classes opt for "supplemental course track" and attend Romani language classes in 3 or 4 hours a week.¹⁸ Supplemental course track, however does not constitute an exemption regarding educational segregation.

Additionally, Law no. 198/2023 on Education contains a separate section of School Desegregation,¹⁹ while Ministerial Order 7701/2024 establishes the mechanism of monitoring educational segregation, including the National Commission for School Desegregation (*Comisia Națională pentru Desegregare Școlară*)²⁰ and county level anti-segregation commissions at School Inspectorates.²¹

In spite of these seemingly progressive trends, Romania's anti-segregation legislation is characterized by severe shortcomings:

- 1) The 198/2023 Law in education, does not focus only on ethnic or racial segregation but next to race and ethnicity it enlists more sets of categories, such as socio-economic status, place of residence and academic performance. Seemingly, this represents a positive tendency in Romania's anti-segregation legislation, as the first official documents concerning segregation, such as Circular no. 29323/2004.04.20 or Decree no. 1540/2007 of the Ministry of Education focused exclusively on segregation of Roma children. Certainly, the inclusion of children with special educational needs is an urgent task too. Nevertheless, focusing on a large number of sets of categories dilutes the effectiveness of anti-segregation policies concerning Roma children.
- 2) The lack of reliable data hinders monitoring and the development of adequate evidence-based policies. Some of the above-mentioned sets of categories (such as socio-economic status) are purely defined. In the case of Roma, SIIR databases could be used for data gathering and monitoring. However, there is a "cacophony" of different techniques of classification, ranging from hetero- to auto-identification. It is not well defined methodologically, whether school directors or the administrative personnel should identify Roma children or parents should self-declare the Roma identity of their children.
- 3) Even more strikingly, the focus of anti-segregation legislation and, especially, the monitoring has shifted from inter-school segregation toward intra-school and intra-class segregation. The ministry of education, for instance, coordinated a report on school desegregation, with the technical assistance of UNICEF Romania and the European Commission (TAIEX) Technical

¹⁷ Art 11, par 4.

¹⁸ Art 59 para 5

¹⁹ Title I, Chapter II, Section 7 (*Desegregare Școlară*).

²⁰ Art 80.

²¹ Art 79. par. 7.

Assistance and Information Exchange using SIIIR data to detect educational segregation along the categories enlisted by the educational law. They focused exclusively on intra-school segregation (across buildings, classes and in classroom level groupings).

1.3. FCNM articles, indicators and empirical data

In order to assess educational rights of Hungarian and Hungarian-speaking Roma children and whether Romania fully implemented its obligations undertaken under the FCNM in relation to minority education, we examine whether the minority education system the state established is also in line with the following provisions of the FCNM:

- **Article 4**, prohibition of non-discrimination and promotion of full and effective equality;
- **Article 4.2**, promotion of effective equality and participation in different societal domains
- **Article 6**, promotion of tolerance and mutual respect
- **Article 12.3**, the principle of equal access to at all levels of education

In presenting the case, we use multiple data sources. To find out how these relate to the articles of the FCNM, see Table 1:

- Our most important data source is an **exhaustive survey of Hungarian and mixed language schools**²² carried out by the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities and Bálványos Institute in cooperation with Transylvania Inquiry and Institute for Public Policies in Szeklerland. We targeted educational units (*unitate plan*), some of them without legal personality and affiliated with a central educational unit. The questionnaire was completed for 885 educational units, representing 97,7 percent of the schools having Hungarian as their language of education. We use this survey to investigate differences in the educational infrastructure, access to extra-curricular activities, the language knowledge of auxiliary personnel, linguistic landscape and extra-curricular language use in mixed schools. For comparative data we also used a previous (2019) **exhaustive survey of Hungarian and mixed language schools**, carried out by Bálványos Institute in cooperation with the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities²³ and Erdélystat.²⁴ The questionnaire was completed by 922 educational institutions, representing 97 percent of the schools having Hungarian as their language of education. We use this survey to investigate extra-curricular language use and differences of resource allocation inside mixed language schools.
- **SIIIR** (Integrated Information System in Education in Romania) database. We used data aggregated at class-level containing information on the number of students by classes and various indicators (such as grade, level of education, form of financing and propriety, profile, method of teaching and language of education). We used especially the 2024 version of this database, but also earlier versions in order to define dropout rates.

²² See the report: <https://ispmn.gov.ro/storage/app/media/ispmnwp-73-05-02-1.pdf>.

²³ <http://ispmn.gov.ro/>.

²⁴ <http://statisztikak.erdelystat.ro/home/?lang=en>.

- **Databases of baccalaureate exam and national examination results** were downloaded from <http://static.bacalaureat.edu.ro>, <http://static.avaluare.edu.ro>, and data.gov.ro sites, restructured and integrated. These are individual level databases containing the results of the baccalaureate and (8th grade) national examination results, including grading for each subject and status of the student (whether he or she passed the exam or does not). Graduates of Hungarian language schools and classes can be distinguished and thus a comparative analysis of the passing rates for the 2017-2024 period became possible.
- Another secondary data source is **PISA** (Programme for International Student Assessment). In the 2022 data collection, following the initiative of the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities (ISPMN), a separate representative subsample was elaborated for students learning in Hungarian. Thus, conclusions concerning the performance of Hungarian learning students can be drawn.

Table 1. Issues, relevant FCNM articles, indicators and data sources

	Issue	Relevant FCNM article	Indicators	Data source
Students learning in Hungarian language	Discrimination of students learning in Hungarian	4	- Differences of infrastructure and teaching equipment between schools and inside schools	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024)
			Unequal access to auxiliary services (speech therapist, psychologist)	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024)
			Unequal access to extracurricular activities	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024) and SIIR database (2024)
	Linguistic asymmetries and asymmetric contact in mixed schools	4, 6, 12.2	- Asymmetries of linguistic landscape in mixed schools - Asymmetric extracurricular language use - Lack of Hungarian speaking personnel	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024)
	Unequal access to education of Hungarian learning students	12.3, 4.2	- Significantly higher dropout rates	SIIR databases
- Significantly lower passing rates in baccalaureate exams (in spite of slightly better results in student assessment programs)			Database of baccalaureate exam results (2017-2024); PISA datasets (2022)	
Hungarian-speaking Roma students	Discrimination of students of Roma origin in Hungarian language schools	4	- Educational segregation	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024)
			- Differences of infrastructure and teaching equipment	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024)
	Unequal access to education of Roma students	12.3., 4.2	- Significantly higher dropout rates	Exhaustive survey of Hungarian language and mixed schools (2019; 2024); SIIR databases

2. Discussion of relevant issues by articles

2.1. Discrimination of students learning in Hungarian (Article 4)

Art. 4.1.

The Parties undertake to guarantee to persons belonging to national minorities the right of equality before the law and of equal protection of the law. In this respect, any discrimination based on belonging to a national minority shall be prohibited.

Art. 4.2.

The Parties undertake to adopt, where necessary, adequate measures in order to promote, in all areas of economic, social, political and cultural life, full and effective equality between persons belonging to a national minority and those belonging to the majority. In this respect, they shall take due account of the specific conditions of the persons belonging to national minorities.

The issue of discrimination is rarely discussed in case of linguistically separated educational systems based on voluntary enrollment. Nevertheless, the requirement to provide equal resources and education of equal quality for minority students is a legitimate requirement in case of institutionally robust, state financed systems of minority language education too. The existence of a robust system of minority education (and the fact that minority parents/pupils can choose between minority and majority language education) does not exempt states from providing equal opportunities for minority children.

Neither FCNM, nor other international treaties obliged Romania to create a state-financed quasi-parallel institutional system of minority education. However, if – due to internal processes of bargaining – Romanian legislators decided to do so and if institutional realities have evolved accordingly, there is an obligation to provide equal resources for minority language schools and classes in order to ensure equal quality for minority children. The opposite leads to the marginalization of the minority group and cannot be regarded otherwise than structural discrimination.

In what follows we investigate the differences between minority- and majority-language-medium education in terms of school infrastructure, access to auxiliary services, access to extra-curricular activities and extra-curricular language use. We demonstrate the existence of discriminatory treatment through statistical indicators.

2.1.1. Disparities of school infrastructure

Our representative survey suggests that there are disparities in school infrastructure to the detriment of Hungarian-language schools, our this. It is clear that the provision of gym, psychology offices, medical offices and ballrooms is lower among exclusively Hungarian-language educational units

compared to the mixed-language ones (Figure 2). Differences are connected to regional and rural-urban disparities, the educational infrastructure of rural educational units in the Hungarian majority Székely Land (Harghita, Covasna country) being well below the average.

Figure 2. Educational infrastructure outside the classroom in Hungarian and mixed language schools (2019, 2024)

Source: Exhaustive surveys of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2019; 2024)

The 2019 survey pointed out another problem, namely that within mixed schools with both Hungarian and Romanian-language classes, there was a significant difference in classroom level infrastructure, namely equipment with modern teaching tools. In Hungarian language classes the proportion of rooms equipped whiteboards, internet connections, computers, projectors and smart TVs was lower than in the case of Romanian-language classes (Figure 3). As an important result, the 2024 data survey show – mostly due to the favorable context created by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (*Planul Național de Reziliență și Redresare*) – a significant improvement of classroom level educational infrastructure, while differences between Romanian and Hungarian language classes have disappeared in this respect (Figure 3). One problem remains, however: intra-school resource allocation and differences between Hungarian and Romanian language classes are not systematically monitored by relevant authorities.

Figure 3. Equipment with modern teaching tools in mixed schools with both Hungarian and Romanian medium language classes (2019; 2024)

Source: Exhaustive surveys of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2019; 2024)

2.1.2. Unequal access to extra-curricular activities

State financed extra-curricular activities are organized under the umbrella of so-called Children Palaces (*Palatul Copiilor*), which are county-level organizations operating under the school inspectorates. These institutions organize various activities from sport to cultural events. Many of the activities are language dependent, such as acting, literary and ethnographic study groups or musical education. These activities are exclusively in Romanian with the exception of the two Hungarian majority counties of Harghita/Hargita and Covasna/Kovászna. This means that access of Hungarian learning students to state financed extra-curricular activities is rather limited. Practically, due to the lack of state support, these activities are usually organized by Hungarian churches, NGOs, or the parents themselves. Compared to the massive state support for extra-curricular activities in Romanian language, this could be regarded as a form of discrimination. This is most striking in counties with high proportion of Hungarian students and Hungarian inhabited micro-regions, which systematically lack state financing for extra-curricular activities.

In the case of extracurricular activities organized by the schools, differences in access can be observed between homogeneous Hungarian and mixed schools. Each of the listed activities (i.e. student's council, the choir, the folk-dance group, student newspaper, school radio and drama club) are more likely to be accessible in separate Hungarian language schools, while access to these facilities in mixed schools is rather limited (Figure 4; 5).

Figure 4. Extracurricular activities available in Hungarian language in separate Hungarian and mixed language schools (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 5. Extracurricular activities available in Hungarian language in separate Hungarian and mixed language high-schools (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 5 focuses exclusively on high-schools where the likelihood of the enlisted extracurricular activities is higher. In contrast to separate Hungarian upper secondary schools, in mixed schools students can join significantly fewer activities. Moreover, Hungarian students can access these activities even less likely in their native language.

2.21.3. Unequal access to auxiliary services

Article 67 (5) of the 198/2023 Law on Education made mandatory to employ speech therapist and educational counselor (school psychologist) in all educational units, and Article 59 (9) also requires their knowledge of the minority language. Nevertheless, institutional realities do not correspond with this legislative intention. These professionals are employed in lower proportions in separate Hungarian educational units: 71% of them employing psychologist and 26% of the speech therapist compared to 84% and 33% in mixed schools. However, in mixed schools, these professionals often do not speak Hungarian. Since these are language-dependent services, the lack of language skills of staff in mixed schools practically excludes Hungarian students from these services. In addition, there are proportionally fewer assistants, librarians and doctors in Hungarian educational settings than in mixed schools.

Figure 6. Access to auxiliary services in Hungarian language and mixed schools (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

2.21.4. Linguistic asymmetries in mixed schools: extracurricular language use and linguistic landscape

Asymmetric extra-curricular language use in mixed schools was a longstanding and recurrent problem and it was in the focus of grassroots language rights advocacy during previous reporting periods. According to the shadow report of the Civic Engagement Movement (CEMO) in Târgu Mureș,²⁵ for instance, extra-curricular language use and linguistic landscape within mixed schools were profoundly asymmetric and this established a hierarchical relation between minority and majority students attending these schools. According to the decision 172/04.05.2011 of the National Council for Combating Discrimination (NCCD), the lack of bilingual signs inside and at the façade of schools should be considered discrimination and a violation of the rights of minorities to use their language in extracurricular context.

During the 6th legislative period positive change has occurred: the newly adopted 198/2023 Law on Education regulates the use of minority languages outside the classroom in more detail and explicitly. Notably, it made certain elements of minority-language extracurricular communication mandatory in schools offering instruction in minority languages. Specifically, the new legal framework establishes the following:

- **Non-teaching staff language competence (Article 59(9)):** As already mentioned, it mandates that teaching school counselors and speech therapists must demonstrate professional competence in that minority language. In case of other non-teaching positions minority language knowledge is not mandatory. Nevertheless, to foster a truly inclusive environment and to enable non-teaching personnel to effectively carry out their duties, it is also important that secretaries, librarians, security guards, and nurse possess minority language skills. Consequently, alongside the legally mandated roles, our survey also assessed the linguistic competences of personnel in these auxiliary positions.
- **Bilingual linguistic landscape and written communication (Article 59(11)):** The law explicitly requires that in educational institutions with minority language instruction, all common spaces, information boards for students and teachers, and displays of any kind must be inscribed in both Romanian and the respective minority language. This provision covers inscriptions on school façades, public announcements, timetables, the official websites and social media pages of the schools, and the internal signage of classrooms, administrative offices, rooms for auxiliary services.

The language proficiency of non-teaching personnel is essential not only for access to auxiliary services but for minority language or bilingual oral communication. Figure 7 assesses the Hungarian language skills of the personnel across six positions. The figure refers to schools where the given position exists. We considered that a school meets the requirement if at least one employee in a given position was proficient in Hungarian.

²⁵ <https://cemo.ro/en/cemo-shadow-report/>

Figure 7. Hungarian language knowledge of the non-teaching personnel in Hungarian and mixed language schools (2019; 2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2019; 2024)

According to our results, students in Hungarian-only schools can generally use their mother tongue orally in extra-curricular context, even if a slightly negative trend was detected concerning the Hungarian language knowledge of secretaries and security guards. In mixed schools, however, the reality is radically different. Only 66% of existing psychologists and 61% of speech therapist speak Hungarian (in spite of the fact that in case of these positions Hungarian language knowledge is mandatory). In case of librarians, nurses and secretaries these proportions are around or below 50%.

The official linguistic landscape of an educational institution serves as a highly visible indicator of minority language use. Key elements include exterior signage on school façades, internal inscriptions for specific rooms, and the language used for timetables and public announcements. Furthermore, official websites and social media platforms (such as Facebook) play an equivalent role in the digital space.

Our survey reveals a disparity between school types regarding all forms of written communication. In Hungarian-only schools, bilingual signage and communication are widespread (Figures 8; 9): 92% display bilingual signs on their façades, and 95% communicate in Hungarian on their official Facebook pages. Other domains show slightly lower, yet still robust, figures: 86% display timetables in Hungarian, 85% maintain a Hungarian-language website, and 77% translate official announcements. Internal room signage follows a similar pattern, with 76% to 81% of surveyed spaces featuring bilingual inscriptions. However, it is a point of concern that Hungarian language use has decreased across almost all communication channels, most notably regarding official announcements, which saw an 11% decline.

Figure 8. Bilingual inscriptions and written communication in Hungarian and mixed language schools (2019; 2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2019; 2024)

Figure 9. Bilingual inscription of special rooms in Hungarian and mixed schools (2019; 2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2019; 2024)

Conversely, the linguistic landscape and written communication in mixed-language schools remain overwhelmingly monolingual in Romanian. The notable exception is façade signage, where 60% of these schools employ bilingual signs. In all other categories, schools utilizing Hungarian constitute a minority: 24% for official announcements, 30% for websites, 32% for timetables, 36–40% for internal signage, and 48% for Facebook pages. Although there has been marginal progress in certain areas since 2019 (such as social media and internal signage), this is offset by regressions in other domains, such as announcements. Ultimately, most mixed schools continue to resist making the Hungarian language visible in shared educational spaces.

2.2. Asymmetrical contact between Hungarian and Romanian speaking students in mixed schools (Articles 6 and 12.2)

Art 12.2.

In this context the Parties shall inter alia provide adequate opportunities for teacher training and access to textbooks, and facilitate contacts among students and teachers of different communities.

Art. 6.1.

The Parties shall encourage a spirit of tolerance and intercultural dialogue and take effective measures to promote mutual respect and understanding and co-operation among all persons living on their territory, irrespective of those persons' ethnic, cultural, linguistic or religious identity, in particular in the fields of education, culture and the media.

Art. 6.2.

The Parties undertake to take appropriate measures to protect persons who may be subject to threats or acts of discrimination, hostility or violence as a result of their ethnic, cultural, linguistic or religious identity.

Discrimination of Hungarian students and asymmetries in extracurricular language use in mixed schools are problematic from another perspective too. On the one hand, they can be perceived as indicators of the language ideology permeating these institutions. On the other hand, however, these aspects not only mirror asymmetric interethnic relations and majority dominance characterizing mixed schools but also affect the process of socialization of schoolchildren and reproduce the perception that minority members should accept a subordinate position. If in mixed schools Hungarian students are marginalized and discriminated against, these institutions will barely produce mutual respect and a spirit of tolerance.

Both the *Commentary on Educational Issues under FCNM* and country opinions issued by the Advisory Committee express a clear preference for integrated education. The main motive is that in case of a linguistically separate institutional systems contact between minority and majority students

is often limited.²⁶ Nevertheless, contact (and mixed schools as its most obvious institutional form) can contribute to tolerance, intercultural dialog mutual respect and cooperation only if it is based symmetrical relations between majority and minority group members. Indeed, discriminative practices and asymmetric institutional environment are often evoked by experts and stakeholders when justifying pursuits for separate Hungarian-medium-language schools. These considerations also inform the choices of Hungarian parents when they enroll their children in separate instead of mixed language medium schools.

2.3. Educational segregation of Hungarian-speaking Roma students (Article 4)

2.3.1. Roma students in Hungarian language schools

According to our exhaustive survey (relying on estimations of the administrative staff of schools), the total number of Roma pupils enrolled in Hungarian language education in 2024 was of 16,017 or 14% of the total student population. Our survey targeted 0-4 (primary), 5-8 (lower secondary), 9-11 (upper secondary short-term professional), 9-12 (upper secondary long-term professional, vocational and high schools) and post-secondary education (Figure 10). Differences between these educational levels are dramatic, indicating a very high level of dropout rate, especially between lower and upper secondary levels. The proportion of Roma students in of 20.2% among primary, 15% among lower secondary, 8.5% among short term upper secondary and almost negligible among long-term upper secondary students.

The proportion of Roma among students learning in Hungarian is the highest in the North-Western part of the country (Satu Mare and Bihor counties), where, in spite of the ethnically and linguistically mixed character of the population, the vast majority of Roma is Hungarian-speaker and is enrolled in Hungarian language education (Figure 11).

Roma students constitute a larger proportion in rural (28.7% at primary level) areas and small towns (22.9%), compared to larger urban centers (*municipii*, 7.9%). This latter is connected to two factors (1) concentration of Roma in economically peripheral regions due to the ethnic selectivity of internal migration and (2) the phenomenon of “white flights”, meaning that non-Roma parents from rural areas increasingly tend to enroll their children in schools in nearby cities, especially if the proportion of Roma students is rising (Figure 12).

²⁶ See among others paragraph 46 of the first and paragraph 121 of the 2nd County Opinion on Estonia, paragraph 51 and 74 of the 1st and paragraph 70 of the 3rd Country Opinion on Macedonia, paragraph 72 of the 4th Country Opinion on Slovakia.

Figure 10. Roma children enrolled in Hungarian language education (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 11. The proportion of Roma students at primary level in Hungarian language education by counties (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024); SocioRoMap (2017)

Figure 12. The proportion of Roma students at primary level in Hungarian language education by counties and type of settlement (2024)

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

2.3.2. Educational segregation in Hungarian language education: a quantitative perspective

Research and minority rights advocacy focusing on education of Roma distinguishes between three types of educational segregation, namely (1) within class; (2) within school and (3) between schools. As already mentioned, the Romanian legislation and monitoring system focuses on within class and within school segregation. The aim of our shadow report is to describe between schools' segregation of Roma students enrolled in Hungarian language education.

According to the results of our exhaustive survey, the 878 educational units teaching in Hungarian can be classified into four categories, depending on the proportion of Roma students in the Hungarian section (Table 2):

(1) **Segregated Roma schools**, where the proportion of Roma is above 50%. The number of such units is 143 and 10.4% of all students studying in Hungarian (11,740 students) and 55.2 percent of Roma students (8,834 Roma students) studied here. The overall proportion of Roma in the Roma-majority sites is 75.2 percent.

(2) There are 85 educational sites with a **strong Roma presence** (30-49 percent), where there are 8,170 students (7.2 percent of all students studying in Hungarian), including 3,249 Roma students (20.3 percent of Roma students). The overall proportion of Roma in the sites with a strong Roma presence is 39.8 percent.

(3) **Roma presence** (10-29 percent) was recorded in 154 educational settings, where 15,776 students (13.9 percent of students), including 3,093 Roma students (19.3 percent of Roma students), study. The total Roma proportion in these settings is 19.6 percent.

(4) **Minimal or no Roma presence** (below 10 percent) was recorded in 496 settings, where 68.5 percent of all students (77,550 students) study, and the number of Roma is 833 (5.2 percent of Roma students). The proportion of Roma in these settings is 1.1 percent. 80 percent of non-Roma students study in settings characterized by minimal Roma presence.

Table 2. The distribution of students learning in Hungarian by type of educational site

Educational units	Ed. units	Students					
		Roma		Non-Roma		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Roma majority	143	8,834	55.2	2,906	3	11,740	3
Strong Roma pres.	85	3,249	20.3	4,921	5.1	8,170	5.1
Roma presence	154	3,093	19.3	12,683	13	15,776	13
Minimal Roma pres.	496	833	5.2	76,717	78.9	77,550	78.9
Total	878	16,009	100	97,227	100	113,236	100

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 13. The distribution of Roma students by the type of educational unit at primary and

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Our data indicate a rather high degree of the ethno-racial segregation inside the Hungarian language education and this tendency is even more pronounced at elementary level, where 60% of Roma students are enrolled in segregated educational units. 5,886 Roma students study in Roma-majority educational settings, while in settings with a strong Roma presence and characterized by a Roma presence, the figures are 18% each, 1,755 and 1,785 students, respectively. The proportions at lower secondary level are 51 for Roma majority, 21 for strong Roma presence and 23 percent for Roma (2,816, 1,137 and 1,289 Roma students) (Figure 13).

The educational segregation of Roma is much stronger in cities and towns than in villages, where “only” 56 and 46 percent of Roma students study in primary and lower secondary education in Roma-majority educational settings. These proportions are 74-74 percent in small towns and 71 and 61 percent in cities. Since the proportion of Roma students in municipalities is much lower than in villages and small towns, desegregation efforts would have been theoretically more possible in these settlements (Figure 14).

Figure 14. The distribution of Roma students by the type of the educational unit by settlement type at primary level

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Regionally, educational segregation is higher in the North-Western counties of Satu Mare and Bihor. Here, the proportion of Roma children learning in segregated schools of is 75 and 74 percent at primary, and 69 and 67 percent at lower secondary level, which is also due to the fact that the proportion of Roma in rural and small-town educational settings is much higher than in the counties

of Covasna, Mureş and Harghita. Here 54, 54 and 51 percent of Roma learn in Roma majority schools at primary, and 38, 41 and 43 percent at lower secondary level (Figure 15).

Figure 15. The distribution of Roma students by the type of the educational unit by county at primary level

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

2.3.3. Educational consequences of educational segregation: lower quality education for Roma children

The next question is whether separate education of Hungarian-speaking Roma children should be considered segregation and whether it is discriminatory? According to Law no. 198/2023 the answer is unequivocally affirmative. As already mentioned, Article 11 of the law enlists the exceptions where the education in separate groups of certain categories should not be considered segregation. Native language education provided for national minorities, special education for children with severe disabilities and groups accommodating immigrant and refugee children are among them, while the separate education of Roma children in Hungarian language medium schools clearly does not figure. Moreover, article 3 of the Law emphasizes that segregation is a severe form of discrimination and it is against the organizing principles of Romania’s educational legislation and policies.

International minority rights protection also emphasizes that, next to respect for norms of cultural pluralism and the right of minority parents to identity transmission, education for minority children should provide equal social and professional opportunities for minority children. It is often presumed that, while separated education is a more proper tool of identity reproduction, integrated education

serves better the goal of participation on equal footing and equal opportunities.²⁷ Thus, anti-discrimination is usually associated with pursuits for integrated education and some important decisions of the European Court of Human Rights condemning educational segregation of Roma pupils also used arguments of discrimination.²⁸

In practice, two criteria should be used to decide whether separate education of minority children is discriminatory and, thus, should be considered as educational segregation. First, if the education of minority children in separate groups, classes or schools is not upon the request but against the will of minority parents, separate education is clearly discriminatory and constitutes educational segregation. Second, if minority students enrolled in segregated institutions receive lower quality education than the majority, discrimination is even more obvious.

Taking into account the above mentioned two criteria, the separate education of Roma children in Hungarian language schools is obviously discriminative. First, according to broad and in-depth qualitative and quantitative research standing behind the *Strategy of Social Inclusion of Roma in Harghita County*,²⁹ Roma parents would prefer integrated education. Although Hungarian educational stakeholders often emphasize that Roma students “prefer to be among themselves”, according to multisite field research, Roma parents usually do not consider that segregated education is advantageous for their own children. Second, according to our exhaustive survey of Hungarian and mixed language schools, the infrastructural facilities of Roma majority educational settings are below average (Figures 16-17), as-well-as their access to auxiliary services (Figure 18). Moreover, the qualification of teachers employed in such units is below the average of Hungarian language schools (Figure 19).

²⁷ Ringelheim, Julie: Between Identity Transmission and Equal Opportunities: The Multiple Dimensions of Minorities’ Right to Education. In Henrard, Kristin (ed.): *The Interrelation between the Right to Identity of Minorities and their Socio-economic Participation*. Brill-Nijhoff, Hague, 2013, 91 – 114.

²⁸ D.H. and others v. the Czech Republic (13 November 2007), Sampanis and others v. Greece (2 June 2008) and Orsus and others v. Croatia (16 March 2010) are such cases.

²⁹ https://hargitamegye.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/Anexa_1.pdf

Figure 16. Educational infrastructure outside the classroom by the type of the educational unit

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 17. Modern teaching equipment in classrooms by the type of the educational unit

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 18. Access to auxiliary services by the type of educational unit

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

Figure 19. The qualification of teaching personnel by the type of the educational unit

Source: Exhaustive survey of Hungarian and Mixed Language Schools (2024)

2.3.4. Educational segregation in Miercurea-Ciuc: a qualitative case study

Miercurea Ciuc (*Csíkșzereda* in Hungarian) is a typical middle-sized city (*municipiu*) in the Hungarian majority area of Székely Land. According to 2021 census data, its population was of 34.484, with 82% Hungarians and 17% Romanians. Officially, the number of Roma was of 246, less than 1% of the population, nevertheless, according to SocioRoMap survey their number was 700, the majority of them living in segregated Roma neighborhoods. There are two larger compact Roma neighborhoods in Miercurea Ciuc, one in Șumuleu (*Csíkșomlyó*) district and one in Tavaszi Street (*Tavaszi utca*). In the latter, the Roma actually live in two separate settlements. In addition, there are two other locations where Roma families live geographically concentrated, in Szécsény, in the social houses managed by Caritas, a charity organization connected to the Roman Catholic Church and in Petőfi street (in the city center). There is a smaller number of families of Roma origin living dispersed in the city, in areas that are not considered as Roma neighborhoods by locals. These families, some of them musicians, others former industrial workers, play an important role in the cultural and social life of the city. Their role is decisive in the local Roma self-organization. Nevertheless, in everyday life, they are invisible to the majority. Thus, when people of Miercurea Ciuc talk about “Gypsies”, they usually refer those living in the compact Roma neighborhoods.

Figure 20. Roma neighborhoods and segregated Roma schools in Miercurea Ciuc

Residential segregation has clearly intensified after the change of regime. The Tavaszi street “colony”, next sewage treatment plant (called “Shit Factory” or *Szargyár* in Hungarian by locals) was established

as a result of forced evictions following the restitutions of formerly nationalized properties situated downtown (Petőfi street) and the privatization of workers' hostels, serving as home for Roma families. It is worth highlighting that in 1990, more than 70% of the housing stock in Miercurea-Ciuc was state-owned. However, while the privatization process generally meant that non-Roma people got their own homes at nominal and extremely low prices, many Roma families lost their homes and ended up in the city's Roma settlements. This left them with rather precarious housing conditions that made formal labor market integration and equal social participation illusory from the very beginning of the democratic transition.

Moreover, deteriorating housing conditions are coupled with a rather rigid system of educational segregation. The vast majority of Roma students, and virtually all students living in compact neighborhoods end up in Xántus János General School (*Școala Generală Xántusz János*). Xántusz has always operated as a school for the "peripheries" within the city. Its school district encompasses areas that are not geographically connected but are clustered around the core of the city and are considered by the locals as "villages" belonging to the town. Such connected/subordinated villages are Șumuleu (*Csíksomlyó* in Hungarian), Toplița (*Taplca* in Hungarian), Jigodin (*Zsögöd* in Hungarian), Cioboteni (*Csobtfalva* in Hungarian) and Ciba (*Csiba* in Hungarian). All these former villages are part of one school district surrounding the town. Perhaps it is not a coincidence that the Waldorf school, which is in a peripheral position within the education system in terms of educational methodology, has also developed within the institutional umbrella of Xántusz. Its primary section operates in Cioboteni. However, as the Waldorf method has become popular among members of the local intelligentsia and professional middle class, the lower secondary section received a new building downtown from the Mayor's Office.

In a first step, Roma children were channeled into the "schools of the peripheries" (Xántusz) due to increasing residential segregation (following forced evictions) and a specific "gerrymandering" of school districts performed by the Mayor's Office with the compliance of the Harghita County School Inspectorate. Following this gerrymandering, Tavasz street was incorporated into the district of Xántusz and, consequently, Roma student had to be enrolled into the Sub Pădure (*Erdőalja* in Hungarian) Elementary School under its subordination. This happened in spite of the fact that other educational units are by far closer to the Roma neighborhood. Roma children living in the Șumuleu colony were enrolled in the nearby segregated elementary school, close to the main building of Xántusz. At lower-secondary level, both the children from Șumuleu and Tavasz Street attended the main building of Xántusz, situated in Taploca).

School segregation has become even more extreme following a 2024 crisis, when the Roman Catholic Church resigned to continue renting the building of the Șumuleu Primary School to the Mayor's Office. At that time, a container school was established and placed in the yard of the already existing other „Gypsy” primary school and kindergarten (Sub Pădure Primary School). As another important element, the Mayor's Office started a bus service, collects and transports Roma children from other neighborhoods (Petőfi Street and Szécsény), to the Sub Pădure Primary School. Thus, currently, all Roma students study in the same place, actually outside of the borders of the city, in two separate buildings and, officially in two educational units (as the Șumuleu Primary School was maintained in the container). Almost all children in these two educational locations are Roma, except for two or three children from families in Csiba involved in shepherding.

At lower secondary level, Roma students continue to study in the main building of Xántusz. Here, the proportion of non-Roma students is higher, between 25-30%. They are only partly from Taploca (as children from Taploca mostly study in other educational institutions in the city), and partly from the surrounding villages.

Certainly, educational and social consequences of this institutional setting are devastating. If we look at the dropout rates of the educational cohort starting their studies in 2015/2016 and finalizing the 8th grade in 2024, the first significant break appears between 4th and 5th grades, when Roma children are transformed to the main building of Xántusz, when only 23 out of 31 students remain in this educational institution. This is largely due to the fact that non-Roma parents enroll their kids in other schools beginning with the 5th grade, when the Roma children arrive. In other words, it can actually be said that the majority of Roma children (at least “on paper”) reach the 8th grade. However, in 2024, although the vast majority of them appeared at national examination, not a single student scored a passing grade in all subjects (See Figure 20). Thus, only rather few Roma children continue their studies at upper secondary level (all of them in short- and long-term professional education). At the time of our field visit (March 2025) there were only 17 Roma students enrolled in upper secondary schools in Miercurea Ciuc, some of them arriving from nearby villages.

In addition to school performances, this segregated institutional setting reproduces the isolation and alienation of different ethnic communities. The socialization of both Roma and non-Roma children takes place in hermetically separated institutional environments. Moreover, the possibility of Roma children to use public spaces in the town becomes rather limited. It is due to educational segregation that they are simply excluded from public social spaces and public institutions perceived as “owned” by the majority (local Hungarians and Romanians). Thus, the Roma are already in a subordinate position, while the majority can spare themselves any context with them. Educational institutions (similarly to housing) mirror and reproduce local interethnic relations based on exclusion and extreme forms of subordination.

It is worth emphasizing that this type of segregation is neither a ‘natural’ outcome of parental choices nor ‘inevitable’ institutionally, but it is a consequence of inadequate processes of monitoring of educational segregation and orchestrated by local political elites. Moreover, educational segregation happens with the compliance of county level school inspectorate, which authorizes, for instance, a container school placed on the yard of another educational institution. In order to achieve this outcome, the Mayor’s Office performs a “gerrymandering” of school districts. Moreover, the Mayor’s Office does not issue identity cards for Roma but provide temporary IDs only, without an address. Thus, the enrollment of children is no more mandatory for school, who can decide to enroll (non-Roma) out-of-zone for vacant places. The school inspectorate structures the enrollment caps at non-Roma educational units in a way that minimizes such vacancies, while only educational units belonging to the *Xántus János Lower Secondary School* accept Roma children. Other schools, even if they have vacancies, systematically reject applications from Roma families. By establishing the school-bus network the mayor’s office reinforces these decisions assuring that all or most Roma children are enrolled.

2.4. Unequal access to education: higher dropout rates and d and the process of official examination (Articles 12.3 and 4.2)

Art 12.3.

The Parties undertake to promote equal opportunities for access to education at all levels for persons belonging to national minorities.

Art. 4.2.

The Parties undertake to adopt, where necessary, adequate measures in order to promote, in all areas of economic, social, political and cultural life, full and effective equality between persons belonging to a national minority and those belonging to the majority. In this respect, they shall take due account of the specific conditions of the persons belonging to national minorities.

2.4.1. Dropout points in Hungarian-medium education

One of the most severe systemic challenges of the Hungarian language education in Romania is the unequal access of Hungarian students to secondary and tertiary education due to higher dropout rates and lower passing rates at official examinations. Figure 21 uses SIIR data and compares the dropout rates of Hungarian learning students in the case of the educational cohort starting preparatory (0th) grade in the 2012/2013 and graduating (finishing 12th grade) in the 2024/2025 school-year. The entry point (preparatory grade) represents 100% and the figure shows the proportion of students who were still in the educational system at higher grades. Overall, 68% of the students in Romania was still in the educational system at the time of finishing the 12th grade (in 2024/2025), while in case of Hungarian learning students this figure was of 53%. The proportion of those passing the baccalaureate examination and, thus eligible for tertiary education, was of 51% for the country as a whole and 41% for Hungarian-learning students.

Figure 21. School leaving and dropout points in Hungarian-medium education in Romania (2012/2013 school cohort; students starting preparatory class = 100%)

Calculations based on 2012/2013-2024/2025 SIIR data

Based on Figure 21 we can identify several dropout points, such as lower secondary education, starting upper secondary education, 12th grade and baccalaureate examination. In this section we also distinguish between three factors conducting to unequal educational outcomes and unequal access of Hungarian learning students to secondary and tertiary education:

1. **Early school leaving and higher dropout rates.** Driven by an interrelation between socioeconomic factors (the generally lower position of Hungarian speakers in Romania's system of ethnic stratification)³⁰ and structural discrimination, this aspect is also connected to segregation of Roma children in Hungarian language education.
2. **Structural disparities in secondary tracks:** A disproportionately high proportion of Hungarian-learning students are channeled into short term professional education that does not offer baccalaureate examination, thus cutting their access to higher education.
3. **Lower passing rates at official examination:** Lower success rates in the 8th grade National Evaluation and the 12th grade Baccalaureate Examination are driven almost entirely by inadequate testing in Romanian Language and Literature, which – even after reforming the examination – seems to fail to treat minority students as non-native speakers.

Before discussing the above-mentioned factors two further remarks should be made. First, significantly higher early school leaving and dropout rates among Hungarian-medium create severe

³⁰ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-78893-7_11

barriers of access to both secondary and tertiary education and explain the underrepresentation of Hungarians among university graduates across all age groups (Figure 22).

Figure 22. The proportion of university graduates among Hungarians and Romanians by age group according to 2021 census results

Source: 2021 census results

Table 3. PISA case numbers and results by language medium of education and language used at home

		2006	2009	2012	2015	2018	2022
N (case number)	Majority (Romanian) students	4838	4423	4693	4343	4613	5906
	Hungarians in native lang. education	146	222	222	396	233	1219
	Hungarians in majority lang. education	133	102	43	38	59	39
Mathematics (PV)	Majority (Romanian) students	415	445	445	431	428	415
	Hungarians in native lang. education	435	444	439	459	453	435
	Hungarians in majority lang. education	397	419	430	392	381	397
Reading (PV)	Majority (Romanian) students	396	438	433	426	430	396
	Hungarians in native lang. education	412	456	443	467	446	412
	Hungarians in majority lang. education	374	381	422	354	382	374
Science (PV)	Majority (Romanian) students	418	438	432	429	427	418
	Hungarians in native lang. education	446	465	471	472	464	446
	Hungarians in majority lang. education	403	402	421	363	386	403

Source: OECD, PISA databases

Second, it was a widespread hypothesis that Hungarian language education is in general of lower quality compared to the Romanian language one. Nevertheless, the 2022 PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) survey, which had a representative subsample of Hungarian language learners, showed that the performance of Hungarian language learners was above the national average.

2.4.2. Early school leaving during lower-secondary education

Negative trends in early school leaving of Hungarian learning students becomes evident at lower secondary level. The decrease of Hungarian learning students exceeds the national average already at 5th grade also due to shift to majority language education of some of the Hungarian language students at the beginning of secondary level. The further decrease of the educational cohorts between 5th-8th grades is, however, closely connected to the educational segregation of Roma children. As a combined consequence of language shift and higher dropout rates, only 86% of the 2015/2016 educational cohort was in the (Hungarian language) educational system by the end of the 8th grade, compared to the national average of 91%. Decomposing data to the categories of the type educational units according Roma presence, it becomes evident that higher drop-out rate characterizes segregated Roma educational units, while in case of units with no or minimal Roma presence early school leaving is less characteristic compared to the national average.

Figure 23. Dropout rates during grades 5–8 of the 2015/2016 educational cohort (finalizing 8th grade in 2024) by the type of the educational unit

Source: SHIR databases (2020/2021-2023/2024); <http://static.avaluare.edu.ro>

As Figure 23 shows, the proportion of Roma is not only strongly correlated with higher dropout rate but it is also a factor conducting to dramatically lower performances (passing rates) at 8th grade National Evaluation. At the end of the 2023/2024 school year, in case of segregated Roma educational units 82% of the students starting lower their secondary education four years earlier were still in the system, 57% were enrolled to perform the examination, 43% were present at the examination and only 6% achieved passing score in all subjects. Similarly, negative trends are visible in schools with strong and moderate Roma presence, where participation and passing rates also remain far below national average and units with no or insignificant Roma presence.

2.4.3. Structural disparities of upper-secondary education

In Romania there is a two-level system of national examination with 8th grade examination (National Evaluation) after finishing lower secondary and a Matura Examination (Baccalaureate) for students finishing long term, usually 4 years long, upper secondary education. One should emphasize that in Romania student selection into different educational tracks happens relatively early, at the age of 15. This selection (connected to the results of the National Examination) is rather conclusive with regards to their further educational carrier and, consequently, their later employment opportunities.

Four types of upper secondary schools can be distinguished. The first one is short term upper secondary education (in Romanian *școli profesionale*) that takes three years and offers a certificate of professional qualification but does not allow for baccalaureate examination and tertiary educational enrolment. Long term upper secondary education is of three types: theoretical (*licee teoretice*), technological (*licee tehnologice*) and vocational (*licee vocaționale*). Theoretically, graduates of these tracks can take the baccalaureate exam and, consequently, can opt for tertiary education. However, passing rates of baccalaureate examination were rather different between these types of schools. 90% in case of theoretical, 81% in case of vocational and only 58% in case of technological high schools in 2025.

Figure 24 compares the structure of Hungarian language education to the national average and shows that students studying in Hungarian – in addition to a higher proportion dropout rate following lower secondary education – are channeled in higher proportion toward short-term upper secondary education. This factor also affects negatively the proportions of those who can be enrolled to baccalaureate examination and, thus, may become eligible to tertiary education. This structure, pushing young Hungarians in less favorable labor market positions is not only a form of structural discrimination but it is also a consequence of educational ideologies prevalent among Transylvanian Hungarian educational experts and political class. According to our interviews, many stakeholders and decision makers prefer short-term over long-term secondary education, connected to the influence of educational planning in Hungary and Viktor Orbán’s “assembly plant” concept.³¹

³¹ Orbán preferred short term education over long term secondary and tertiary one due to lack of labor force in the export-oriented industrial sectors in Hungary dominated by foreign, especially German, capital. This orientation has penetrated among Transylvanian Hungarian educational stakeholders and decision makers.

Figure 24. The distribution of 9th, 10th and 11th grade students by educational tracks in 2025

Source: SIIR database 2024/2025.

2.4.4. Trends in official examination results

2.4.4.1. Legislative changes

The actual methodology of the National Evaluation (8th grade examination) was adopted by an ordinance of the Ministry of Education in 2009.³² According to this, students finishing the lower secondary education take written exams in Romanian language and literature and mathematics. Those studying in minority language medium classes are examined additionally in the language and literature of the given linguistic group. Students are examined through uniform tests nationwide. Those studying in minority language classes are examined in their language of tuition (e.g., the minority language, except Romanian language and literature). This unitary form of National Evaluation replaced individual entrance examinations organized by each school. Currently, students are distributed between upper secondary educational institutions via a computerized system based on the results of the national examination, the average grades of each year of lower secondary education and the student's previously proclaimed preferences.

The Baccalaureate Examination takes place after 12th grade, and in its current form it is regulated by Law no. 198/2023 on Education.³³ Students finishing long term upper secondary education have the

³² 4848/31.08.2009 ordinance of the Ministry of Education.

³³ Articles 102 and 103.

right to take the baccalaureate examination. Students in Romanian-language-medium schools should take six exams, among them three written ones, namely Romanian language and literature, one compulsory subject (mathematics or history depending on their profile) and one optional subject. In addition, oral exams are taken in Romanian language and literature and foreign language and a practical exam in computer skills. In case of these latter three exams presence is the only condition of passing, while in case of written exam participants should achieve a minimal grade of 5 for each subject (grading is between 1 and 10). As an additional condition, candidates should achieve a minimal GPA of 6, calculated as the average of the grades taken in the three written exams. Students learning in minority language-schools take two additional exams, namely an oral and a written one in native language and literature. GPA is calculated as the average of the grades on the four written exams. They are examined in the minority language, except Romanian language and literature.

The methodology of the baccalaureate examination was relative stable following 1989, nevertheless its significance and context has changed radically after 2010. First, currently the baccalaureate examination is practically the only examination that students take in order to enter tertiary education. Previously, students had to take the baccalaureate, but, additionally, universities organized separate entrance examination. Baccalaureate was a minimal condition, but entrance did not depend on baccalaureate results. Second, in 2011 cameras were introduced in examination rooms and in this context passing rates declined abruptly (before 2011 there was a widespread conviction that the results of the baccalaureate are not reliable, and that cheating was widespread). Third, in 2015 another change occurred: exams are corrected exclusively by teachers of counties different from where the examination took place.

On the whole, Romania has moved toward a more unitary, standardized and centralized model of national examination and student selection following 2010. This might be legitimate, however, as we will see, the changes have disproportionate negative effects for students learning in Hungarian language medium classes limiting their further educational and employment opportunities.

According to Article 46(2) of Law no. 1/2011 on Education and the methodology adopted by the Ordinance of the Ministry of Education no. 5671/2012, “*the subject Romanian language and literature is taught based on syllabi and schoolbooks specially elaborated for the minority in question throughout the whole pre-university school year*”. This provision is also confirmed by Article 60(9) of Law 2023/198 on Education. However, the regulation came into force gradually, starting with students enrolled in the 2013-2014 school year. Minority students who started their studies before the 2013-2014 school year, with the exception of elementary education, studied the Romanian language and literature based on the curriculum developed for Romanian-speaking classes. According to this gradual approach students taking National Evaluation are examined according to special tests elaborated for minority students beginning with school year 2020-2021, while those taking the baccalaureate beginning with 2024-2025.

2.4.2.2. 8th grade National Evaluation

Passing rates in case of both 8th and 12th grade examination are significantly lower for students studying in Hungarian-language-medium classes. Importantly, this happens in the context where the results of international assessment programs show that students studying in Hungarian-medium classes do not underperform compared to their colleagues enrolled in majority language medium schools (Table 3).

Figure 25 illustrates the differences in the 8th grade National Examinations results based on individual-level databases available at static.evaluare.edu.ro and data.gov.ro. We also used the SIIIR databases, from which we queried the number of students at the end of 8th grade representing 100% and divided into five categories: (1) not registered; (2) did not appear; (3) achieved a grade below 5; (4) achieved a grade above 5; above 5 for all subjects.

Figure 25. 8th grade National Evaluation results of Hungarian and Romanian learning students

Source: SIIIR database 2024/2025; <http://static.evaluare.edu.ro>

Figure 25 shows that students learning in Hungarian underperform due to two factors. First, they register and appear on the exam in lower proportions. Second, they pass in slightly lower proportions the mathematics and in drastically lower proportion the Romanian language and literature examination. Importantly, the change of the methodology of the examination and special tests elaborated for minority language speaking students did not lead an improvement of their performance.

Figure 26. Passing rates at 8th grade National Evaluation among Hungarian and Romanian learning students by subjects

Source: <http://static.avaluare.edu.ro>

2.4.2.3. Bacalaureate examination

Although individual level databases on bacalaureate results are accessible (static.bacalaureat.edu.ro and data.gov.ro sites), determining passing rates poses some challenges. Next to these sources we used SIIR database in order to determine the number of 12th grade graduates. At Figure 27 the total number of graduates represent 100% and is divided into five categories: (1) not registered; (2) did not appear; (3) failing to pass; (4) passing during autumn session; (5) passing during summer session.

Figure 27. Bacalaureate examination results of Hungarian and Romanian learning students

Source: *static.bacalaureat.edu.ro*; *SIIR (2024/2025)*

It is a widespread phenomenon that schools – in order to increase artificially success rates – do not allow academically underperforming students to sit the exams.³⁴ According to analysisist, this phenomenon is less widespread in Hungarian-language-medium schools and, consequently, Hungarian students are examined in higher proportions.³⁵ Figure 27 confirms this tendency. Nonetheless, passing rates among Hungarian students were constantly lower compared to the national average in the period between 2017 and 2024.

Lower passing rates of Hungarian students was caused exclusively by their weak performance at Romanian language and literature exams, where, before 2025, they needed to fulfill the same requirements as Romanian monolinguals. The seemingly impartial practice that written exams are corrected in other counties also created disadvantage for Hungarian students. Their tests in many cases were evaluated by teachers living in regions without significant Hungarian population and without taken into account that they were performed by non-native speakers. One should also highlight widespread (and unfounded) stereotypes among majority group members that Hungarians are not willing to learn Romanian. This also often leads to a high level of intolerance concerning the incorrect Romanian language. These widespread negative attitudes, e.g., the “native-languageism” of the majority, might have affected the bacalaureate results of Hungarian-speaking students.

³⁴ Hatos, Adrian – Curta, Iosif: A test of the effect of denominational schools in Romania. *Central European Journal of Educational Research*, 2020 (2): 4.

³⁵ Barna, Gergő: A magyar nyelvű oktatás versenyképessége Romániában. *Érettségi eredmények, 2012–2016* [The competitiveness of Hungarian language education in Romania. Bacalaureate results 2012-2016]. *Regio* 2019 (4): 146.

Figure 26. Passing rates at Bacalaureate Examination among Hungarian and Romanian learning students by subjects

Source: static.bacalaureat.edu.ro

3. Conclusions and recommendations

Romania’s educational policies are instrumental in identity maintenance and group reproduction. Our report did not focus, however, on identity reproduction aspects of minority education but explored:

- (1) the systemic discrimination of Hungarian-speaking students that is present
 - a. in unequal resource allocation for Hungarian language schools,
 - b. unequal access to extra-curricular activities,
 - c. unequal access to auxiliary services, such as school psychologist and speech therapist,
 - d. and asymmetrical language use inside mixed schools;
- (2) the asymmetries of contact between minority and majority students in mixed schools that also pushes Hungarian parents to choose separate Hungarian language schools;
- (3) the direct and indirect discrimination of Roma students inside the Hungarian language educational institutions
 - a. in form of educational segregation,
 - b. unequal resource allocation for Roma majority schools;
- (4) the unequal access to secondary and tertiary education caused by
 - a. higher dropout rates and early school leaving interconnected with educational segregation,

- b. Structural disparities and channeling Hungarian learning students to short term upper secondary education,
- c. Inadequate official examination for Romanian language and literature constituting also a form of indirect discrimination.

3.1. Combating discrimination in resource allocation and language use inside mixed schools (recommendations related to Article 4)

One can notice systematic distortions in resource allocation at the expense of students learning in Hungarian language medium classes. Our exhaustive survey suggested that Hungarian-language schools are less equipped with gyms, psychologist's offices, medical offices and ballrooms due mainly to regional and rural-urban disparities. As a positive tendency, the gap between Hungarian-language and Romanian-language classes in equipment with modern teaching tools inside mixed schools has narrowed considerably. Further, asymmetries and inequalities within mixed language medium schools are difficult to measure and to monitor based on the actual system of data collection. ARACIP, the institution responsible for quality assurance provides only school level data. The exhaustive survey we relied on proved to be a useful instrument, however, from the angle of official data collection it is ad hoc. In order to solve this problem, we recommend the following:

Monitor and bridge the infrastructural gap

Recommendation 1 (for Article 4)

Relevant authorities should regularly monitor inequalities existing inside mixed schools between Romanian-language medium and Hungarian-language medium classes and should intervene in cases where minority students are discriminated in resource allocation. One possible solution would be to empower and allocate budgetary support for the Romanian Institute for Research of National Minorities to run the exhaustive survey focusing on minority and mixed language schools at bi- or triannual basis in cooperation with the Ministry of Education as part of the official monitoring process.

Recommendation 2 (for Article 4)

Relevant authorities also should develop evidence-based policies and establish a dedicated state-funding mechanism to rehabilitate fully Hungarian-language educational facilities, prioritizing the construction of gyms, laboratories, libraries, and counseling offices to bring these schools up to the physical standards of mixed-language schools.

Mixed schools present deficiencies not only in internal resource allocation, but in access to auxiliary services and extracurricular activities. These two factors are partially connected to asymmetries of extra-curricular language use inside mixed language schools. Although these schools have parallel

Romanian and Hungarian language tracks, the linguistic landscape of these institutions is dominantly Romanian, Hungarian language being limited to in-classroom use. Furthermore, as a result of lack of Hungarian-speaking staff, a large number of Hungarian-speaking school children is denied the possibility to use their mother tongue when contacting the school secretariat, library, the speech therapist, or the school psychologist. According to Law no. 198/2023 on Education, specialists occupying these latter two positions should have been Hungarian-speakers.

Recommendation 3 (for Article 4) – Enforce bilingual landscape

More balanced bilingualism, symmetric extracurricular language use, and balanced linguistic landscape should be facilitated in mixed schools in order avoid the discrimination of Hungarian speaking students. Relevant authorities should regularly monitor this process, as it is explicitly regulated by the educational legislation. One possible solution would be to task and allocate budgetary support for the Romanian Institute for Research National Minorities to conduct in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and the National Council for Combating Discrimination (NCCD) systematic audits of schools teaching in the minority language to ensure compliance with Article 59, Paragraph 11 of Law no. 198/2023. Clear deadlines and administrative sanctions must be implemented for schools failing to provide bilingual internal signs, timetables, websites, and official announcements.

Recommendation 4 (for Article 4) – Linguistic competence of auxiliary personnel

Hiring of Hungarian speaking personnel in the key positions of school psychologist, speech therapist in mixed medium language schools should be facilitated in order to provide equal access to these services for Hungarian-speaking students. This process should be also officially monitored.

Also, broaden the linguistic requirements of Law no. 198/2023 to mandate that auxiliary, administrative, and medical staff (secretaries, librarians, nurses, and security guards) in mixed schools possess minority-language skills in the minority language that the school teaches in.

Public finances for extracurricular activities are also rather unevenly distributed. Hungarian language programs exist only in the two Hungarian majority counties of Harghita/Hargita and Covasna/Kovászna. Theoretically, this could mean that state financed extracurricular activities represent an integrated segment of education where teachers and student of different background meet each-other. However, practically, this is not the case and students learning in Hungarian language medium schools (outside the above mentioned two countries) have a limited access to extra-curricular activities. This is the most evident in case of language-related activities such as acting, literary circles etc. In mixed schools these activities are usually not available at school level either.

Recommendation 4 (for Article 4) – Promote inclusive and minority language extracurricular activities

Hungarian language extra-curricular activities should be financed in all countries, preferably in a proportion equal to the share of students learning Hungarian language medium classes. This is the most justified in areas where Hungarians live in higher proportions and concentrated (Mureş/Maros, Satu-Mare/Szatmár, Bihar/Bihor, Sălaj/Szilágy) and in case of language related activities

Minority-language extracurricular activities (theaters, music, school media, and student councils) should also have been promoted in mixed language schools to prevent the cultural exclusion and alienation of Hungarian pupils.

3.2. Facilitate more symmetrical forms contact between majority and minority students in mixed schools (Recommendation in relation to Article 6 and 12.2)

Asymmetric interethnic relations and majority dominance characterizing mixed schools affect the process of socialization of schoolchildren and reproduce the perception that minority members should accept a subordinate position. If in mixed schools Hungarian students are marginalized and discriminated against, these institutions will barely produce mutual respect and a spirit of tolerance.

Recommendation 6 (for Article 6 and 12.2) – Promote symmetric contact in mixed language schools

More equal relation should be promoted inside mixed schools. This should cover both in-school resource allocation and extra-curricular language use. Treating this problem would be necessary to increase the prestige and sustainability of mixed language medium schools.

3.3. Combating educational segregation of Roma pupils in Hungarian language schools (recommendations in relation to Article 4)

Hungarian-speaking Roma children are at the intersection of linguistic of linguistic and ethno-racial discrimination. This situation combined with extremely vulnerable socio-economic situation creates a real human- and minority rights crisis inside the Hungarian language schools connected to educational segregation. More than 55% of Roma students enrolled in Hungarian language education study in segregated, Roma-majority educational units, characterized by severe infrastructural deficits, lack of auxiliary services and a low proportion of qualified educators. Educational segregation is also the main driver leading to devastating dropout rates in lower secondary education. In segregated schools only 6% of the 8th grade students take the National Evaluation, while earlier dropout rates are also far higher than the average among them.

The educational segregation of Hungarian-speaking Roma is neither an ‘inevitable’ socio-demographic process nor a ‘natural’ institutional development but it is facilitated by inadequate processes official monitoring and orchestrated by local political elites in compliance with school inspectorates. As documented in Miercurea Ciuc (Csíkszereda), municipalities and county-level school inspectorates use administrative barriers, such as withholding permanent identity cards from Roma families, to strip children of their geographic school-enrollment rights. Local authorities also actively manipulate school-zoning boundaries, manipulate classroom enrollment caps to prevent integration, and establish segregated busing networks to channel Roma children to peripheral, out-of-town schools. Furthermore, when existing structures fail, regressive and segregated solutions are employed, such as the establishment of isolated “container schools” on the yards of already existing segregated educational sites. These solutions clearly running against existing legislation are utilized instead of integrating Roma children into schools attended by (non-Roma) Hungarian children. This deliberate isolation socializes both majority and minority populations into a rigid, caste-like system, physically banishing Roma children from shared public spaces and reproducing ethnic hierarchy.

Educational segregation of Hungarian-speaking Roma children does not only run against the fundamental principles of the Romanian legislation but, as a severe form of discrimination, also against the implementation of Article 4 of FCNM.

Combatting segregation of Roma children in Hungarian language education (for Article 4)

Recommendation 7 – Monitor and develop evidence-based policies

Official process of monitoring of school segregation of Roma children should be started, including inter-school segregation. Evidence based policies to prevent school segregation should be developed. A concrete, time-bound national strategy to phase out segregated, Roma-majority educational units should be elaborated and implemented, with specific funding lines allocated to the integration of Hungarian-speaking Roma children in the Hungarian medium education.

Recommendation 8 – Eradicate infrastructural inequalities, ban container schools

Resource and infrastructural asymmetries should be eradicated by establishing a funding mechanism to upgrade physical infrastructure, digital tools, and classroom environments in marginalized and segregated rural and urban schools. Crucially, the Ministry of Education must ban the use of "container schools" as a permanent or long-term alternative to physical integration, ensuring all students have equal access to standard school facilities.

Recommendation 9 – Qualified personnel in Roma majority schools

Introduce financial and professional incentives (e.g., allowances, career acceleration points) to attract and retain certified, highly qualified educators in segregated, and rural schools.

Recommendation 10 – Monitor school zoning and ban discriminatory “gerrymandering”

Ban discriminatory school-zoning and administrative gerrymandering. The Ministry of Education, in conjunction with the National Council for Combating Discrimination (CNCD), must audit local

school-zoning boundaries and municipal busing routes to ensure they are not being actively used to bypass neighborhood integration and channel Roma children to peripheral schools.

Recommendation 11 - Eradicate identity document barriers to education.

The Ministry of Internal Affairs and local municipalities must end the practice of issuing temporary identity cards to Roma families as a tool of spatial containment. All children, regardless of their parents' housing registration status, must be granted full, unconditional enrollment rights in the public schools closest to their real physical place of residence.

Recommendation 12 - Enforce strict accountability for local school inspectorates.

Establish a monitoring mechanism to investigate and penalize county-level school inspectorates that artificially adjust student enrollment caps for any reason whatsoever, and school directories systematically reject Roma applicants to keep majority-ethnic schools segregated.

3.4. Facilitating more equal access of Hungarian students to secondary and tertiary education (recommendations in relation to Article 12.3. and 4.2.)

The most serious problem affecting Hungarian-language education as a whole is that students studying in Hungarian reach the 12th grade well below the national average, and that they graduate at a lower rate. In this regard, we identified three factors conducting to dropout and earlier school-leaving. (1) The dropout between grades 5 and 8, affects Roma students, who make up about 20 percent of the student population educated in Hungarian at primary level. (2) unfavorable structure of Hungarian language secondary education and channeling Hungarian students toward short-term secondary education; (3) Lower passing rates of Hungarian students at 8th grade National Evaluation and Baccalaureate examination.

Significantly lower passing rates at baccalaureate examination constitutes one of the most serious disadvantages affecting Hungarian language education. According to results of international assessment programs students learning in Hungarian language medium classes perform slightly better and, in this context, their lower performance at official examination is even more striking. The obvious reason for this was the Romanian language and literature exam, on which until the 2024/2025 academic year tests elaborated for majority students were used in case of Hungarian students too.

Factors lying beyond the low performance of Hungarian students can be investigated now more rigorously, as a separate subsample of Hungarian speaking students was elaborated in the 2022 wave of PISA. This was a reasonable step, as Transylvanian Hungarians constitute the most numerous student population educated in a minority language in EU member states. In case of many linguistic minorities (having a similar quasi-separate system of native language education) representative subsamples are employed in PISA. Such examples are German speakers in Italy and Belgium, Gaelic speakers in the UK. Russian speakers in Baltic States and Albanians in Northern Macedonia are not

assessed on separate subsamples but due to their proportional weight they are represented in enough numbers in national samples.

Recommendation 13. – Use separate subsample for students learning in Hungarian for quality assurance (for Article 4.2 and 12.1)

In Romania a representative subsample of PISA for student learning in Hungarian is a highly relevant tool of quality assurance, especially given the low passing rate at baccalaureate examination. Keep the practice of elaborating representative Hungarian-language sample in the next waves of PISA too.

Recommendation 14. – Calibrate Romanian language and literature examination 8th grade National Evaluation and Baccalaureate Examination

Calibrate the lower secondary Romanian language and literature curriculum for minority speakers and 8th grade Romanian exam for non-native speakers. Urgent reform is needed for the lower secondary Romanian language and literature curriculum and the 8th grade National Evaluation in Romanian Language and Literature. The exam and the specialized curriculum must be fully calibrated to minority children studying in minority languages, ensuring that it test reflects the linguistic competences of minority children.